

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Yogantari, Made Vairagya, and Dwijendra, Ngakan Ketut Acwin. (2019), Visual Content by Consumer in Promoting Sustainable Culinary Business. In: *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, Vol.2, No.3, 610-615.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.02.03.102

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Visual Content by Consumer in Promoting Sustainable Culinary Business

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Abstract

The creative economy that has begun to get special attention by the Indonesian government opens opportunities for the culinary sector to continue to grow by providing creative added value. Utilizing technological advancements and analyzing consumer's psychographics can help culinary business in promoting their products to the public. Today's consumers have a tendency to share photos they take in a culinary business location on social media. Visual content in the form of photos can be used by culinary business owners for sustainable promotion where content will continue to be provided by consumers. Using descriptive exploratory methods by taking several objects as a case study aims to determine the criteria that trigger consumers to make sustainable digital content for a culinary endeavor.

Keywords: Visual Content, Promotional Media, Culinary Sector.

Introduction

Culinary as a creative economy sub-sector in Indonesia is an industry that can be regarded as an eternal industry. As a primary need, the culinary industry became the first contributor to the Creative Economy (GDP) of the Creative Economy (Ekraf) among 16 other ekraf sub-sectors in 2016 which spread to 34 provinces in Indonesia. Data on the Kompas website states that 41.4 percent was contributed by the culinary sub-sector from the overall contribution of the creative economy, which sum 922 trillion in 2016 (Kompas, 2018). Based on that great potential was then the Creative Economy Agency (Bekraf) to build the culinary industry ecosystem in Indonesia which was divided into several aspects, namely human resources, capital, marketing, intellectual property rights, and infrastructure. With a conducive ecosystem, it will certainly create healthy competition between culinary ventures.

To be able to compete, culinary business is required to have creative added value so that they can follow the lifestyle of today's consumers. Increasing income and the development of digital technology literacy also have an influence on the shift in people's perspectives on culinary business. The culinary business place is no longer just a place to eat, but also a space to gather with friends, meet with clients, and just take self-photos to share with netizens in cyberspace. The shift in consumer's behaviour opens up opportunities for extensive creativity for

culinary business owners to innovate started from the food menu, service, brand identity design, interior design, to visual content as a media campaign in the digital era.

To increase brand awareness or the number of consumers and audiences who know the products of a culinary business, an innovative promotion strategy is certainly needed. Deciding on promotional media that are in line with the era of corruption requires special observation to customers, which becomes the market segmentation of a culinary business. By identifying what is needed and desired by consumers can help culinary business owners compile attractive promotional content by focusing on psychographics from consumers. Psychographic segmentation in marketing or promotion includes consumer attitudes, values, behaviours, emotions, perceptions, beliefs, needs, benefits, hopes, and interests. It becomes important to see how the current behaviour of the community cannot be separated from smartphones (smartphones) so that the creative approach needs to be traced from consumer psychography.

The ease of access to technology and information requires promotional content for any type of product to respond to consumer habits in using applications on their smartphones. Based on the results of the penetration survey of internet users in Indonesia in 2017 by the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII) exposed by Kompas website, 43.89% of Indonesians access the internet 1-3 hours a day, 29.63% access the internet 4-7 hours per day and 26.48 % access the internet more than 7 hours a day. For devices used, 44.16% use smartphones or tablets to access the internet, 4.49% use personal laptops, and 39.28% use a combination of devices such as smartphones and computers or laptops (Rakhma & Setiawan, 2018). Henri Kasyfi Soemartono as Secretary-General of APJII also stated that 89.35% of services accessed by internet users in Indonesia are chat and 87.13% for social media, upload photos on Instagram, Facebook and so on. Looking at the percentage level of social media users in Indonesia, this article aims to find out effective content so that it can help promote sustainable culinary business in the digital era.

Research Method

The analytical method used in writing this article is descriptive exploratory where the author collects general information related to visual content, culinary business, as well as other information relating to the title for observation then described again by analyzing visual literacy. Primary data collection is done by interviewing culinary business owners and taking a number of samples of culinary businesses that have promoted using social media and surveys to culinary business locations. Secondary data is obtained through the results of official surveys issued by associations and government institutions.

Results and Analysis

Visual Content and Consumer Behavior

Technology disruption requires culinary business people to be able to determine promotional media that are in line with technological disruption where physical stores are being shifted by online stores. The ease and convenience of ordering food that can be done using an online application on a smartphone such as Go-Food or GrabFood make consumers reluctant to come directly to the restaurant, so promotions carried out by offline culinary ventures such as posters and flyers are considered no longer effective. In order for culinary business to survive and be compatible with the onslaught of technology that is so strong, promotional activities carried out can follow the "Asset-Light Model" or also known as "Uber of Everything" where all business and industries use digital technology to produce the highest output possible with the least possible assets (Fatahillah, Y & F & Tryaditia, B 2019). The owner of a culinary business can promote using digital technology without providing content but utilizing visual content in the form of photos and videos made by consumers.

Inviting consumers to be interested in coming to a culinary business is a challenge in the digital age. Analyzing psychographics of consumers from the millennial generation or generation Y born in the years 1981-1995 and the initial generation Z, namely the birth of the range 1995-2000 is quite appropriate because the two generations have

a high level of technological use. Psychographically, the two generations have a tendency to enjoy life like going on vacation, attending music concerts and festivals aimed at finding experiences that cannot be missed. Compared to its predecessor generation, the early millennial and Z generations have the values they want to get, such as happiness, passion, diversity, sharing, and discovery (Matt 2019). One way to fulfill their emotional satisfaction is to get pleasure through the use of social media communication media such as Instagram and Facebook. The response from the public regarding the upload of content in the form of certain discoveries that they share on social media, makes them happy and passionate so that culinary efforts can take advantage of the consumer's psychographics to carry out promotions.

Case Studies

1. KYND Community

Located in Seminyak, Bali Indonesia, Kynd Community is a café that sells culinary products from plants. This culinary business packs their food products appealingly so that ordinary consumers upload photos of the food they ordered on their Instagram. The layout of their culinary business is divided into two parts, namely indoor and outdoor.

Fig 1. Instagram photo content @ syndcommunity that comes from consumers' personal uploads. Source: Instagram account from top left to bottom right; @kattvaldez @sandra_kirkov @maawl @gabriellawisdom @davidguison @jacyo__ @zeebalife @jess_dantas

The photo above shows the photos uploaded by visitors to their personal Instagram. By marking Instagram from KYND Community's culinary efforts in their photos, business owners will get notifications and can take steps to share photos of consumers so that promotional activities on Instagram can continue without the need to prepare special content from business owners. The combination of the words "Another Day in Paradise" as well as illustrations of plants build a tropical impression and the island of Bali that can only be found in KYND Community. So that it is not infrequently both foreign and domestic tourists make the photos they take there as proof that they have visited the island of the gods.

2. Mad Pops Artisan Ice Cream

Selling culinary products in the form of coconut-based ice cream, Mad Pops Artisan Ice Cream is a place that must be visited by both foreign and domestic tourists. Although their culinary business space is very small, they use one side of the wall as a place for photographed customers. Fluorescent lights that read "Ice Ice Baby" give a cute,

girly, and stylish impression that makes customers excited to take photos and share them with their friends in cyberspace.

Fig 2. @madpopsbali's Instagram photo content that comes from consumers' personal uploads.

Source: Instagram account from top left to bottom right; @ frd.aml @eika_azam @ yasmine.schouten @shenacinnamon @melissa_davies @ miokato3306 @sonchicc @jenkvieira

3. Give Cafe

Give Café is a sister café of KYND Community. Using the same method, Give Café provides a special corner for consumers to style and take photos. Typical murals with rainbow illustrations create a happy impression and communicate the essence of the brand that the gift to give is a fun activity. Brand is everything that customers and prospective customers think, feel, say, hear, read see, imagine, suspect, and even expect about a product, service, or organization (Middleton 2010).

Fig 3. Photo content on Instagram @ givecafe that comes from consumer personal uploads.

Source: Instagram account from top left to bottom right; @imagne_sa @self_service @janaschulte @thisislisax @dutchonthemove @flywithgem @chichloe728 @jessiekoehler

CONCLUSIONS

From the results of surveys to the field and the collection of photo data on Instagram, it can be observed that at the location of the three case study objects above, there is a special point for consumers to take photos. Space to take photos is relatively narrow but has a characteristic that can highlight the identity of the product. For the KYND Community and Mad Artops Ice Cream Pops cases, these two culinary businesses use an attractive catchline which says that the products sold have a pleasant, friendly, and presentable character. A catchline is a phrase or sentence designed to attract attention, especially in advertisements or story titles, articles, or newspaper items (Merriam-Webster 2019). In the case of KYND Community and Give Café, both of them have interesting visual elements which include color, shape, line, space, texture, and value, namely in the form of illustrations on the wall, commonly called murals.

Consciously or not by consumers, catchline, and murals are what become one of the promotional materials by culinary efforts then viral due to the photo content uploaded on social media by consumers. Fixed complement elements derived from interior design are furniture in the form of tables and chairs for consumers to sit down to enjoy food while taking photos. These interior complementary elements can be seen in the KYND Community and Give Café case studies. The following is a form of implementation of elements or components of visual and interior design that are in the culinary business location so as to make consumers interested in taking photos.

Table 1. Description of Visual Components and Interior Design Elements Owned by Case Studies

Case Study	Mural	Catchline	Furniture
KYND Community	•	•	•
Mad Pops Artisan Ice Cream	-	•	-
Give Cafe	•	-	•

Source: Writer, 2019.

From the table above, it can be concluded that visual content in the form of photos by consumers has three main components, namely murals, catchlines, and furniture. These three components give more value to culinary efforts because consumers get more experience than just coming to eat and creating a special connection to a brand. By understanding the character and behavior of today's consumers, the combination of visual communication, interior design, and digital technology is an added value for culinary endeavors. The use of visual content created by consumers is a continuous promotional aid that can maintain public brand awareness so as to increase business competitiveness in the culinary field. Brand awareness or recognition is facilitated by a visual identity that is easy to remember and easily recognizable.

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